

The Relationship Between the Role of Teachers, The Role of Students, And the School Environment in Physical Education Learning to the Formation of the Profile of Pancasila Students

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to (1) determine the relationship between the role of teachers and the formation of Pancasila student profiles in physical education (PJOK) learning. (2) determine the relationship between the roles of students in the formation of Pancasila student profiles in physical education (PJOK) learning. (3) determine the relationship between the school environment and the formation of Pancasila student profiles in physical education (PJOK) learning. (4) determine the relationship between the roles of teachers, students, and the school environment in the formation of Pancasila student profiles. This study is an ex post facto study with a correlational approach. The study population includes all eighth grade students of SMP Negeri Sleman Regency. The sampling technique used cluster sampling, a probability sampling technique carried out by dividing the population into groups (clusters), then selecting several clusters randomly to be used as research samples, so that all members in the selected clusters become samples. Of the 256 participants who made up the population, 246 participants participated in filling out a questionnaire distributed attractively via Google Form, so that the data was used for further analysis. The research instrument was a closed questionnaire with a Likert scale to measure each variable, while data analysis was conducted using simple linear regression and multiple linear regression with the help of the SPSS version 21 program. The results of the study indicate that: (1) there is a significant relationship between the role of teachers in Physical Education (PJOK) learning and the formation of the Pancasila student profile with an effective contribution of 39.5%. (2) there is a significant relationship between the role of students in PJOK learning and the formation of the Pancasila Student Profile with an effective contribution of 26.3%. (3) there is no significant relationship between the school environment in PJOK learning and the formation of the Pancasila student profile at -29.1%. (4) there is a significant relationship between the role of teachers, the role of students, and the school environment in PJOK learning and the formation of the Pancasila student profile simultaneously with an effective contribution of 22.3%. Thus, the roles of teachers and students are significantly related to the formation of the Pancasila Student Profile in PJOK, while the school environment is not. Simultaneously, the synergy of these three factors contributed 22.3%, with the teacher's role as the most dominant driver.

KEYWORDS: Teacher role, student role, school environment, Pancasila student profile, Physical Education and Health (PJOK) learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The character of students in Indonesia, particularly at the junior secondary school level, has shown a concerning decline. The student character index dropped to 69,52 in 2021, with the most significant decreases observed in independence (56,34) and mutual cooperation (63,97), while religiosity and nationalism remained relatively stable (Basri & Murtadlo, 2021). This trend is partly attributed to changes in learning patterns during the COVID-19 pandemic, which limited social interaction and hindered the internalization of character values (Rohmah, 2019). More broadly, this condition reflects persistent challenges in education, where schools have not fully succeeded in embedding moral values into students' daily practices (Perdana et al., 2018).

Character education is therefore positioned as a strategic approach to fostering students with strong moral foundations and virtuous behavior. It extends beyond cognitive recognition of right and wrong to the cultivation of habitual actions aligned with positive values (Syaharani Pribadi et al., 2023). In the Indonesian education system, this effort is operationalized through programs such as Strengthening Character Education (PPK), which is integrated into the Pancasila Student Profile framework (Rudiawan & Asmaroini, 2022).

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The Pancasila Student Profile, as part of the Merdeka Curriculum, aims to develop students who are not only cognitively competent but also possess strong character and 21st-century skills. It comprises six key dimensions: faith and devotion to God Almighty and noble character, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical thinking, and creativity (Angga et al., 2023; Primantiko et al., 2024; Septiani, 2022). These dimensions highlight the need to balance knowledge, attitudes, and skills within the learning process.

The realization of this profile requires a holistic and integrative approach across all subjects, including Physical Education, Sports, and Health (PJOK). PJOK is uniquely positioned to simultaneously develop physical, cognitive, affective, and social domains (Mulya, 2023). Through structured physical activities, students are exposed to values such as honesty, sportsmanship, discipline, and leadership (Nuraini et al., 2024; Siti K. S. et al., 2024). Moreover, experiential learning in PJOK facilitates the internalization of cooperation, responsibility, and self-awareness through authentic practice (Agustin & Ulfatun, 2024; Shankar et al., 2023).

From a developmental perspective, eighth-grade students are in a transitional stage marked by rapid physical, cognitive, and socio-emotional changes (Pratiwi et al., 2023). At this stage, they are more responsive to learning experiences involving physical engagement and social interaction, positioning PJOK as an effective medium for character formation (Ntuli & Mudau, 2024).

The effectiveness of PJOK in fostering the Pancasila Student Profile is influenced by three interrelated factors: teacher roles, student roles, and the school environment. Teachers act as facilitators, motivators, and evaluators who design innovative learning experiences while embedding character values (Ramadhan et al., 2024; Raibowo et al., 2019). Meanwhile, students are expected to actively participate, demonstrate sportsmanship, and internalize the values gained during the learning process (Kirch et al., 2021).

In addition, the school environment significantly shapes learning outcomes. Adequate sports facilities, a positive school culture, and supportive institutional policies contribute to the effectiveness of PJOK implementation (Naimah et al., 2021; Ripki et al., 2024; Thomas et al., 2025; Bácsné-Bába et al., 2021). A conducive environment enhances student engagement and supports the development of discipline, responsibility and cooperation.

However, empirical observations indicate that student engagement remains suboptimal despite the implementation of interactive teaching practices. Some students exhibit passivity, low self-confidence, and limited understanding, particularly in practical activities. This suggests that successful PJOK learning is not solely determined by instructional quality but also by student participation and environmental support.

Previous studies have confirmed a significant relationship between teacher competence and student character development (Suryani, 2021), as well as a positive association between the school environment and student character (Pertiwi et al., 2024). Nevertheless, studies that comprehensively examine the integrated roles of teachers, students, and the school environment within PJOK learning in shaping the Pancasila Student Profile remain limited.

Therefore, this study aims to analyze the relationships between teacher roles, student roles, and the school environment in PJOK learning and their contribution to the development of the Pancasila Student Profile. The findings are expected to inform the design of more effective learning strategies and provide evidence-based recommendations for strengthening character education in schools.

II. METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach with an ex post facto correlational design to examine relationships among variables without manipulation, as the phenomena under investigation had already occurred (Wahyuddin & Ihsan, 2016; Rustan & Irfandi, 2022). The correlational method was used to determine the degree of association between two or more variables measured quantitatively (Maksum, 2012; Imam & Harries, 2021), and is particularly suitable for studies that do not involve variable manipulation (Hafeez & Hasbi, 2023).

The research was conducted in several public junior high schools in Sleman Regency, with the population consisting of all eighth-grade students. The sample was selected using a cluster sampling technique, in which participants were drawn based on specific groups, resulting in representative samples from several schools and classes (Safitri et al., 2019; Firmansyah & Dede, 2022; Suriani et al., 2023).

The study included three independent variables: teacher role (X_1), student role (X_2), and school environment (X_3) and one dependent variable, namely the development of the Pancasila Student Profile (Y) (Ridha, 2017). Operationally, the teacher role encompassed functions as a facilitator, motivator, and evaluator in PJOK learning; the student role reflected active participation in the learning process; while the school environment included physical, social, and psychological conditions that support learning.

Data were collected using a questionnaire with a four-point Likert scale. The research instrument was developed based on indicators for each variable and underwent expert judgment to ensure content validity, enabling accurate measurement of the

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intended constructs (Ngatman & Susworo, 2022). Construct validity was tested using the product-moment correlation, while reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, with values above 0.70 indicating that the instrument was reliable (Sugiyono, 2019).

Data analysis began with descriptive statistics to describe the characteristics of the data (Sugiyono, 2019). This was followed by classical assumption tests, including normality (Kolmogorov-Smirnov), linearity (ANOVA), multicollinearity (tolerance and VIF), and heteroscedasticity (Glejser), to ensure the suitability of the regression model.

Hypothesis testing was conducted using simple linear regression and multiple linear regression analyses to examine both partial and simultaneous relationships among variables (Sugiyono, 2019). The level of significance was set at 0.05. Additionally, the coefficient of determination (R^2) was used to determine the contribution of independent variables to the dependent variable, while standardized beta coefficients were employed to identify the most dominant variable (Sugiyono, 2019).

III. RESULTS

This study involved 246 students from four public junior high schools in Sleman Regency, Indonesia. The variables examined included teacher role (X_1), student role (X_2), school environment (X_3), and the Pancasila Student Profile (Y).

A. Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive analysis indicates that most variables are distributed within the moderate and low categories. The teacher role variable has a mean score of 69.894, with the largest proportions in the moderate (30.49%) and low (26.42%) categories. The student role variable has a mean of 99.911, predominantly in the low (41.46%) and moderate (39.02%) categories. The school environment variable shows a mean of 33.443, with the majority classified as low (53.25%) and very low (17.48%). Meanwhile, the Pancasila Student Profile variable has a mean score of 99.285, with the largest proportions in the low (45.53%) and moderate (25.61%) categories. These findings suggest that, overall, the observed variables have not yet reached optimal levels.

B. Classical Assumption Tests

The results of the classical assumption tests confirm that the data meet the requirements for regression analysis. The normality test shows a significance value of 0.104 (> 0.05), indicating a normal distribution. Linearity tests indicate that all independent variables have linear relationships with the dependent variable (Sig. > 0.05). Multicollinearity testing shows tolerance values greater than 0.10 and VIF values below 10, indicating no multicollinearity. Additionally, heteroscedasticity testing reveals that all significance values exceed 0.05, suggesting the absence of heteroscedasticity.

C. Partial Regression Analysis

The regression analysis results show that:

1. Teacher role has a positive and significant effect on the Pancasila Student Profile ($\beta = 0.316$; $p < 0.001$).
2. Student role also has a positive and significant effect ($\beta = 0.265$; $p = 0.002$).
3. School environment shows a negative and non-significant effect ($\beta = -0.132$; $p = 0.059$).

D. Multiple Regression Analysis

The multiple regression analysis indicates that the model is statistically significant, with a value of $F = 23.160$ ($p < 0.001$). This result demonstrates that teacher role, student role, and school environment simultaneously influence the Pancasila Student Profile.

E. Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination shows that $R^2 = 0.223$, indicating that 22.3% of the variance in the Pancasila Student Profile can be explained by the independent variables, while the remaining 77.7% is influenced by other factors outside the model.

F. Standardized Coefficients

Based on the standardized beta coefficients, teacher role has the strongest influence ($\beta = 0.316$), followed by student role ($\beta = 0.265$), while school environment shows a weak and non-significant negative influence ($\beta = -0.132$).

G. Summary of Results

The findings indicate that teacher role and student role are significant predictors of the Pancasila Student Profile, whereas the school environment does not have a significant effect. Although the regression model is statistically significant, its explanatory power is moderate.

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IV. DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that both teacher role and student role have a positive and significant effect on the development of the Pancasila Student Profile, whereas the school environment does not show a significant effect. These findings suggest that character formation in educational contexts is not primarily determined by structural factors, but rather by the quality of pedagogical interactions occurring within the learning process. In other words, the success of value internalization depends more on how values are enacted in instructional practices than on their mere presence in policies or facilities.

The teacher role emerges as the most dominant factor, indicating that teachers remain central agents in the process of value transformation. This finding reinforces the view that teachers function not only as knowledge transmitters but also as key actors in character formation through modelling, facilitation, and instructional management (Kemendikbud, 2022). In the context of physical education (PJOK), the intensity of social interaction and experiential learning further strengthens this role, as teachers do not merely teach values but actively demonstrate them in practice. This is consistent with (Ibrahimi, 2021), who emphasizes the teacher's role as a moral exemplar, and (Saputri et al., 2024), who found a strong relationship between teacher modeling and student character development. However, the dominance of the teacher role also implicitly indicates that the transition toward fully student centered learning has not yet been fully achieved.

On the other hand, the significant influence of student role highlights that value internalization cannot occur passively. Students must be actively, reflectively, and meaningfully engaged in the learning process for values to be effectively constructed. This aligns with the constructivist perspective, which positions students as active agents in building knowledge and character through direct experience (Puspita, 2025; Luthfiyani et al., 2025). In physical education, the experiential, collaborative, and socially interactive nature of learning further supports this process, as emphasized in experiential learning theory (Kolb, 2013). Previous studies also confirm that active student participation is strongly associated with improved character development outcomes (Saputra et al., 2022; Lestari et al., 2024; Fadlillah et al., 2025; Nurafiati et al., 2025). Thus, the student role should not be viewed as complementary, but rather as fundamental to the process of value internalization.

In contrast, the non-significant effect of the school environment reveals a gap between theoretical assumptions and empirical reality. Theoretically, the school environment is considered a crucial component of the educational ecosystem influencing individual development (Elza, 2025). However, these findings suggest that a supportive environment does not automatically translate into effective character formation. This may be due to the lack of integration between the physical environment and pedagogical practices, resulting in the environment functioning merely as a backdrop rather than an active contributor to learning experiences. Prior studies also indicate that the school environment only becomes impactful when it is consistently managed and meaningfully embedded in daily learning practices (Lina, 2021; Silvi Sahpitri, 2025; Bayar & Karaduman, 2021). Therefore, the non-significant finding does not negate the importance of the school environment, but rather suggests that its influence may be indirect or mediated by other variables.

Simultaneously, the three variables explain 22.3% of the variance in the Pancasila Student Profile, indicating that character formation is a complex and multicausal process. The relatively low explanatory power suggests that other factors such as school culture, leadership, family support, and broader socio-cultural contexts may play a more substantial role but were not included in the current model. Nevertheless, the dominance of teacher and student roles underscores that character formation is more strongly shaped by interactive pedagogical dynamics than by structural conditions alone.

Overall, these findings reinforce the paradigm that the development of the Pancasila Student Profile cannot rely solely on structural provisions or formal policies, but must be realized through interactive, reflective, and experience-based learning practices. Teachers act as primary drivers, students as active agents, and the school environment as a supporting factor whose effectiveness depends on the extent to which it is integrated into the learning process.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that both teacher role and student role in physical education (PJOK) positively contribute to the development of the Pancasila Student Profile, while the school environment does not show a significant effect and tends to function as a supporting factor. Teachers play a strategic role as facilitators, mentors, and role models in internalizing character values, whereas active student engagement is essential in fostering meaningful learning experiences. Simultaneously, these three variables collectively contribute to the development of the Pancasila Student Profile, indicating that the process is dynamic and requires synergy among teachers, students, and the learning environment. The findings imply the importance of optimizing teachers' roles as role models, enhancing students' active participation, and providing a supportive school environment. Theoretically, this study supports Social Learning Theory, Self-Determination Theory, and the ecological approach, emphasizing that direct interaction and active engagement play a more decisive role in character formation than environmental factors alone.

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